

APPLYING GAMES TO THE EFL CLASSROOM IN TEACHING YOUNG LEARNERS

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Annotation. The article focuses on the significance of games in teaching young learners in EFL classroom. Games play an important role in improving young learners' comprehension and role of games in teaching grammar and vocabulary is clarified in this paper.

Key words and expression: game-based, student-focused activities, vocabulary, grammar, young learners, TPR, CLT.

Аннотация. В статье основное внимание уделяется значению игр в обучении младших школьников на уроках английского языка. Игры играют важную роль в улучшении понимания младшими учащимися, и в этой статье разъясняется роль игр в обучении грамматике и словарному запасу.

Ключевые слова и выражения: игровая, студенческая деятельность, лексика, грамматика, молодые учащиеся, TPR, CLT.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada ingliz tili darslarida kichik yoshdagi o'quvchilarni o'rgatishda o'yinlarning ahamiyatiga e'tibor qaratilgan. O'yinlar kichik yoshdagi o'quvchilar tomonidan tushunishni yaxshilashda muhim rol o'ynaydi va ushbu maqola grammatika va lug'atni o'rgatishda o'yinlarning rolini tushuntiradi.

Kalit so'z va iboralar: o'yin, o'quvchilar faoliyati, lug'at, grammatika, kichik yoshdagi o'quvchilar, TPR, CLT.

When compared to teaching teenagers or adults, teaching young students is far more challenging because the latter are prone to distraction. Since kids enjoy playing and having fun, teachers should select appropriate teaching strategies that reflect kids' personalities. One strategy to keep students from getting bored in class is to play games. In the teaching of any foreign language, they play a unique role. Games in the classroom are advantageous for both students and teachers. Additionally, by using games, particularly while teaching vocabulary, teachers can accomplish all of the educational goals.

To teach young learners English vocabulary, a variety of techniques and strategies could be employed. A wonderful technique to teach youngsters

language vocabulary is by using actual objects that they can subsequently visualize. They must listen to and repeat the term that is being taught to them. There is also the direct technique, which forbids speaking in one's mother tongue and does not require translation. The only things utilized in the course are entire sentences in the target language. Due to children's hyperactivity, physical activity, and inability to focus for extended periods of time, teachers frequently employ the Total Physical Response (TPR) method as an alternative. Additionally, educators who work with young pupils promote communication by emphasizing language meaning in context through the Communicative Language Approach (CLT).

Most teachers think of games as a time consumer and only a game. However, games in teaching young learners play a crucial role in their comprehension of a foreign language. As Sungurtegin and others explain that “ by playing games, a child makes acquaintance with his environment, learns new life and gain new instructions”.¹ Yolageldili counted some advantages of using games like they reduce anxiety of children in learning foreign grammar, student-focused activities require active involvement of learners, games bring real life situations to the classroom and makes the lesson authentic.² There are some ideas mentioned by McCallum:

1. focus students' attention on specific structures, grammatical patterns, and vocabulary items.
2. can function as reinforcement, review and enrichment.
3. involve equal participation from both slow and fast learners.
4. can be adjusted to suit the individual age and language levels of the students.
5. contribute to an atmosphere of healthy competition, providing an outlet for the creative use of natural language in a non-stressful situation.
6. can be used in any language teaching situations and with all skill areas (reading, writing, speaking or listening).³

Halliwell (argued that due to the creative language skill young learners bring into the classroom, teachers have to provide them with a communicative atmosphere where they could express themselves. ⁴Teachers must also urge students to actively create language for themselves because the language used in

¹ Sungurtekin, Ş., Sezer, G. O., Bağçeli-Kahraman, P., & Sadioğlu, Ö. (2009). The views of pre-service teachers about creative drama: A study according to gender. *İlköğretim Online*, 8(3), 755-770. Retrieved on 14-January-2010, at URL: <http://ilkogretim-online.org.tr/vol8say3/v8s3m11.pdf>

² Yolageldili, G., Arıkan A. (2011). Effectiveness of Using Games in Teaching Grammar to Young Learners. *Elementary Education Online*, 10(1), 219-220

³ McCallum, G. P. (1980). 101 word games: For students of English as a second or foreign language. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

⁴ Halliwell, S. (1992). *Teaching English in the Primary Classroom*. New York: Longman.

any activity is unpredictable. Games are valuable and significant because of this. Not only are they enjoyable, but they also encourage communication and establish regularity.

When teaching vocabulary to young students using games, qualified teachers who engage the students in play and are fluent in the linguistics of the language are required. Rixon stated that understanding games will help teachers in finding and creating games that make their students learn while they play.⁵

When playing a game, students take an active part, encouraging student-centered activities. When played in small groups, students could develop their skills of disagreeing in a polite way, asking for help, and working with others⁶. They encourage cooperation, team spirit, competition, and turn taking⁷. Gardner stated that games encompass a number of intelligences such as visual intelligence when games involve drawing, interpersonal intelligence when they include playing with others, and kinesthetic intelligence when they provides hands-on elements like cards.⁸

Ameer Bakhsh explains the importance of learning and teaching vocabulary in foreign languages and effectiveness of using games in teaching vocabulary to young learners. In mentioning the importance of vocabulary he states David Wilkins statement, "Without grammar very little can be conveyed, without vocabulary nothing can be conveyed". In explaining the importance of using games in teaching vocabulary he uses examples of games "Hot Potato", "Pictionary", "memory Challenge" and others.⁹

There are some suggestions given by Hong about using games in teaching young learners:

- a. When giving instructions to beginners, a few words in the mother tongue would be the quickest way to make everything clear. More English exposure is needed at a later stage.
- b. Games are best set up by demonstration rather than by lengthy explanation.
- c. It is very important not to play a game for too long. Students will begin to lose interest. It is best to stop a game at its peak.¹⁰

⁵ Rixon, S. (1981). How to use games in language teaching. London: Macmillan.

⁶ Jacobs, G. M., & Kline, L. K. (1996). Integrating language functions and collaborative skills in the second language classroom. *TESL Reporter*, 29, 21-33.

⁷ Ersoz, A. (2000). Six games for EFL/ESL classroom. *The Internet TESL Journal*, 6(6).

Orlick, T. (2006). *Cooperative games and sports: Joyful activities for everyone*. Champaign, IL: Human Kinetics.

⁸ Gardner, H. (1999). *Intelligence reframed: Multiple intelligences for the 21st century*. New York, NY: Basic Books.

⁹ Bakhsh S. A. (2016). Using Games as a Tool in Teaching Vocabulary to Young Learners. *English Language Teaching*; Vol. 9, No. 7, 120-128.

¹⁰ Hong, L. (2002). Using games in teaching English to young learners. *The Internet TESL Journal* (August, 8),

The time when games are played is also a crucial feature to pay attention to and Rinvolucri's clarification in this place is worth stating:

- a) before presenting a given structure, especially to find out diagnostically how much knowledge is already known by the learners;
- b) after a grammar presentation to see how much the group have grasped;
- c) as a revision of a grammar area.¹¹

Playing games helps students become more adept at using language in conversation. With the help of grammar games, students can develop their ability in using language as they are given a chance to use language in the situations which have a purpose.¹² Celce-Murcia and Hilles claim that when English language learners participate in games, the language they use is taskoriented and their aim is more than producing the correct speech.¹³ Therefore, games give students a chance to practice grammar in a communicative setting as long as the games draw their attention to some particular forms prior to the communicative practice. When this is accomplished, using games to deepen the relationship between form and discourse is possible because the form(s) being drawn attention to already exist in the wider discursive context that games offer. In essence, by teaching grammar rules and forms in a conversational manner, games give students the chance to drill and practice them. In conclusion, with the addition of communicative skills, games—which had previously been considered time fillers or leisure activities—started to emerge as an essential component of any English as a Foreign Language teaching program.

Even though games are quite popular with young students, they shouldn't be used excessively. They should be selected in accordance with the context, level, and interests of the students. It must also be concerned with the vocabulary and the issue being discussed. Any game can be successful if it is used appropriately for the subject and is overseen by a knowledgeable and professional teacher.

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¹¹ Rinvolucri, M. (1990). Grammar games: Cognitive, affective and drama activities for EFL students. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

¹² Deesri, A. (2002). Games in the ESL and EFL class. The Internet TESL Journal (September 9), [On-line serial]: Retrieved on 05-March-2008, at URL: <http://iteslj.org/Techniques/Deesri-Games.html>

¹³ Celce-Murcia, M., & Hilles, S. (1988). Techniques and resources in teaching grammar. Oxford: Oxford University Press. p 132

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